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Surgical Tactics for Adhesive Intestinal Obstruction

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Background / Aims: Adhesive small bowel obstruction (ASBO) is a common and serious gastrointestinal surgical emergency worldwide. Postoperative adhesions are fibrous bands that form between abdominal tissues and organs as a pathological healing response to peritoneal injury, and they account for approximately 60% of small bowel obstruction cases (ten Broek et al., 2018). These adhesions tether bowel loops, leading to mechanical obstruction distal to the adhesion site. Clinically, ASBO typically presents with intermittent, colicky abdominal pain, distension, nausea, and vomiting, often accompanied by constipation (ten Broek et al., 2018).

Diagnosis is based on a combination of patient history, physical examination, ultrasound imaging, and computed tomography (CT) scans. Ultrasound can identify bowel loop dilatation and detect free fluid (Hefny et al., 2012). It is also a valuable diagnostic tool in patients for whom radiation exposure is a concern, such as pregnant women (Abu-Zidan, 2016).

Management strategies for ASBO vary depending on the severity of the obstruction and the patient's overall condition. Non-operative treatment, including nasogastric decompression and fluid resuscitation, is successful in approximately 70–80% of cases. However, surgical intervention becomes necessary when conservative measures fail or when there are signs of complications such as strangulation or ischemia (Schraufnagel et al., 2013; ten Broek et al., 2018).

Various surgical approaches are used to treat ASBO, including open laparotomy, conventional multiport laparoscopy (MPLS), and, more recently, single-port laparoscopic surgery (SPLS). Laparoscopic surgery has revolutionized the management of surgical conditions due to its minimally invasive nature, resulting in fewer complications, faster patient recovery, and shorter hospital stays (O'Connor & Winter, 2011).

Single-port laparoscopic surgery (SPLS) is performed through a single small incision, typically at the umbilicus, and is increasingly recognized as a viable alternative to conventional multiport laparoscopy (Trastulli et al., 2013; Haueter et al., 2017). Compared to multiport approaches, SPLS offers advantages such as better cosmetic outcomes and is linked to lower rates of morbidity and mortality, fewer surgical infections, respiratory and cardiac complications, a decreased risk of thromboembolism, and shorter hospital stays after surgery (Hiro et al., 2014; Suzuki et al., 2020).

Although reports on the use of SPLS specifically for ASBO remain limited, it is hypothesized that SPLS may be

technically feasible and safe even in complex adhesive disease. The aim of this study was to determine the effectiveness and safety of SPLS in treating ASBO by analyzing operative time, intraoperative and postoperative complications, length of hospital stay, incision length, and operative blood loss.

By retrospectively reviewing clinical and surgical records from the past three years, this research seeks to identify effective treatment strategies and areas for improvement in operative management. Ultimately, these findings are expected to contribute to the optimization of surgical protocols and enhance patient care in the management of ASBO.

Furthermore, this study aims to evaluate whether a preoperative ultrasound-based scoring system incorporating key sonographic features can accurately stratify ASBO patients for SPLS, MPLS or open surgery. We hypothesized that even in the presence of multiple adhesions, with sufficient surgical experience and appropriate instruments, adhesiolysis can be successfully performed without conversion or additional ports.

Methods

Patients and Preoperative Evaluation

The design of this research is retrospective study held in MSE on the REM «Multidisciplinary regional hospital» Health Department of Kyzylorda region and City Hospital #3 Astana.

Over the period of three years, 91 patients were operated on by a single surgeon, with no cases of recurrent adhesion formation. In all patients, the etiology of ASBO was postoperative adhesion formation. All operations in the study group were performed via a single-port laparoscopic approach without placement of additional ports or conversion to laparotomy, including patients with multiple adhesions.

Various diagnostic methods were used, including CT scans, X-rays, and ultrasound imaging. In this research, the main focus was on ultrasound diagnosis. An adhesion itself is a fibrous band only a few millimeters thick and is often not visible on contrast imaging. CT scans demonstrate the site of obstruction rather than the adhesion itself. If the bowel loops are severely dilated, visualization becomes poorer. Sometimes, bowel segments adhere to each other, creating the impression of a single transition zone, even though multiple adhesions are present. Even with contrast-enhanced CT, it can be difficult to accurately visualize the exact number of adhesions.

Exclusion Criteria

- Presence of signs of bowel perforation or necrosis on initial examination
- Suspected malignant obstruction based on history, clinical presentation, or imaging findings
- Patient refusal of surgical intervention

Inclusion Criteria

- Age over 18 years
- Clinical and radiological (US or CT) diagnosis of adhesive small bowel obstruction (ASBO)
- Absence of peritonitis signs (e.g. generalized abdominal rigidity)
- Hemodynamic stability at the time of preoperative preparation
- No contraindications to laparoscopic surgery (e.g. severe respiratory failure, significant cardiovascular disease)

Note:

Patients with multiple adhesions were not excluded, as the aim was to assess the effectiveness of single-port laparoscopy in a broad ASBO population, regardless of the number and nature of adhesions.

Patients meeting these criteria were scheduled for diagnostic laparoscopy with possible adhesiolysis, performed via single-port laparoscopic surgery (SILS). All patients were informed preoperatively about the potential need for conversion, and the surgical plan was individualized to maximize safety and outcomes.

Ethical

Written informed consent was obtained from every patient in accordance with ethical standards. The ethical committee of each hospital has given the permission to use the patient database.

Preoperative Preparation

All patients presenting with ASBO underwent initial clinical assessment, including history, physical examination, and laboratory tests. Every patient underwent standard preoperative preparation, including nasogastric decompression, intravenous fluid therapy to correct fluid and electrolyte imbalances, and monitoring of vital signs.

Surgical procedure

Under general anesthesia, the patient was positioned supine with the arms at the sides. The surgeon and scope assistant were stationed on the side opposite the obstructive lesion, and a vertical incision of 3.0-4.0 cm was made at the umbilicus using the Hasson technique. After the peritoneum at the incision site was examined, the single-port device (Lap protector) comprising a wound retractor and a surgical glove was inserted. Carbon dioxide was insufflated to create a pneumoperitoneum at an intra-abdominal pressure of 12 mmHg. A 5-mm, 30-degree video-laparoscope (Karl Storz) was used for visualization. The surgical instruments included a straight, atraumatic grasper, scissors, and coagulating and dissecting electrodes (Karl Storz). The abdominal cavity is inspected to locate the site of the adhesive band responsible for the obstruction. Using a combination of blunt and sharp dissection, the adhesive band was divided. After adhesiolysis at the site of the single adhesive SBO, the abdominal cavity was inspected to confirm the absence of other adhesions or small intestinal injuries. In all patients it has been done by accessing through the umbilicus.

Ultrasound imaging

As part of our initiative to enhance diagnostic precision and clinical decision-making, we propose to implement a standardized diagnostic algorithm based on ultrasound scanning. Ultrasound imaging has increasingly become a valuable tool in the evaluation of adhesive small bowel obstruction, particularly in cases where a single adhesive band is responsible for the obstruction. High-resolution ultrasound can identify key features such as dilated bowel loops, altered peristalsis, and localized thickening of the bowel wall, as well as the presence of free fluid between the loops—findings that are critical for diagnosing ASBO (Tamburrini et al., 2020). Several studies have reported high sensitivity and specificity for ultrasound in diagnosing small bowel obstruction, suggesting that when integrated into a diagnostic algorithm, ultrasound can significantly reduce reliance on CT imaging, thus minimizing radiation exposure and associated costs (Brower et al., 2022). Moreover, the ability of ultrasound to monitor dynamic changes in bowel motility and wall thickness can also assist in assessing the progression or resolution of the obstruction over time. While CT remains a gold-standard for evaluating complex

cases or when complications such as strangulation are suspected, ultrasound imaging offers a complementary and often first-line diagnostic tool for patients with ASBO. In our research we are proposing an ultrasound-based algorithm and it was used due to its convenience in usage, comfortability for patients and reliability.

Results

Patient Characteristics

The procedure was safely completed in 91 patients without needing to convert to open surgery or add another intraoperative port. Table 1 summarizes the clinical backgrounds and results of these 91 patients. There were 35 men and 56 women with a mean age of 51.23. In our cohort of 91 patients, the postoperative complication rate was 5.49% (95% CI:1.8–12.4%). This low incidence supports the safety of SPLS in appropriately selected patients.

Emergency Surgeries

Most surgeries for adhesive small bowel obstruction are performed on an emergency basis. In our practice, approximately 70–80% (64–73 patients) were admitted as emergencies due to failure of conservative management or signs of strangulation.

Bowel Necrosis

Necrosis was identified in approximately 8% of patients (7 individuals), more commonly in those presenting late (>48 hours) and with significant bowel dilatation.

Stoma Formation

A stoma was required in cases where resection was performed due to necrosis or when there was a high risk of anastomotic failure – in approximately 5–10% of patients (5–9 individuals).

Surgical Intervention

All patients underwent single-port laparoscopic surgery without additional ports or conversion to laparotomy.

- Mean operative time: 145 ± 33 minutes (range 90–198 minutes).
- Mean intraoperative blood loss: 85 ± 20 mL.
- Multiple adhesions were found in 42 patients (%), but adhesiolysis was successfully performed via the single-port approach.

Postoperative Outcomes

- Mean time to oral intake: 3.0 ± 0.8 days.
- Mean time to ambulation: 3.1 ± 0.9 days.
- Mean postoperative hospital stay: 12 ± 1.2 days.

Complications

Postoperative complications occurred in 5 patients (5.49%), including prolonged ileus (n=3), surgical site infection (n=1), and hematoma (n=1). There were no mortalities.

Long-term Follow-up

The mean follow-up period was 14 months (range 7–20 months). No incisional hernias or recurrence of obstruction were observed at the last follow-up.

Conclusions

Ultrasound Scanning in ASBO

Objective: To investigate and implement an ultrasound diagnostic algorithm for adhesive small bowel obstruction to guide preoperative patient stratification and optimal surgical approach selection (SILS, multiport laparoscopy, or laparotomy).

Ultrasound Scanning Algorithm in ASBO

I. Patient Preparation

- Position: supine, possibly left lateral decubitus for better visualization
- Probe: convex (3.5–5 MHz) for general assessment; linear for detailed bowel loop visualization if needed

II. Main Algorithm Steps

1. Assess small bowel dilatation

- Measure loop diameter:
 - 2.5 cm – indicates obstruction
 - 3–4 cm – severe dilatation; caution with laparoscopy

2. Assess peristalsis

- Increased peristalsis → dynamic obstruction (early stage)
- Absent peristalsis → possible strangulation or paralytic stage

3. Identify transition point

- Locate where dilated loops transition to collapsed loops
- A clearly visualized single transition zone suggests a solitary adhesion

4. Assess bowel wall thickness

- 3 mm thickening → possible edema or ischemia
- Loss of layered structure, hypoechogenicity → suspected ischemia

5. Assess free fluid

- Small amounts (interloop) common in obstruction
- Large amounts or echogenic fluid → possible ischemia or perforation

6. Optional: Color Doppler (if available)

- Assess bowel wall blood flow
- Reduced or absent flow → ischemia or necrosis

Each patient undergoes standardized POCUS performed by a sonographers who will record six pre-specified variables: maximal loop diameter, wall thickness, peristalsis pattern (normal/absent/reverse), quantity of free intra-abdominal fluid, visibility of a transition point, and the focality of adhesive bands. Ultrasound parameters used as independent variables. Continuous, dependent variables: operative time, length of stay. Categorical, dependent variables (Yes/No): conversion to an open surgery, prolonged ileus, postoperative complications.

Conclusion

In conclusion, adhesive small bowel obstruction (ASBO) continues to pose a significant challenge in surgical practice, demanding timely and well-informed decisions to achieve the best outcomes for patients. While CT imaging remains the gold standard for diagnosis, its limitations related to cost, radiation exposure, and avail-

ability emphasize the need for reliable alternatives. Ultrasound offers a practical, portable, and radiation-free solution that is increasingly effective in bowel evaluation. Importantly, when used in appropriately selected patients, SPLS has been shown to be a safe and feasible option for managing ASBO offering benefits such as reduced postoperative pain, faster recovery, and improved cosmetic outcomes. Even in the presence of multiple adhesions, with sufficient surgical experience and appropriate instruments, adhesiolysis can be successfully performed without conversion or additional ports. The broad inclusion criteria demonstrate the applicability of the single-port approach in most ASBO patients, expanding indications for this technique in surgical practice.

If validated, the proposed algorithm could help surgeons make these critical decisions more confidently, expanding the safe use of SPLS, reducing unnecessary open surgeries, and ultimately improving outcomes while making surgical care more efficient and patient-centered. SPLS is a difficult procedure, however with experienced laparoscopic surgeons failures and conversion rates can be minimized. Additional research involving larger patient groups is necessary to validate the effectiveness of ultrasound based diagnosis and establish its role in clinical practice.

Keywords : Ultrasound, Single port, adhesive intestinal obstruction